

University-industry collaboration in Brazil: Co-authorship in scientific articles

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Abstract

The present research in progress investigates university-industry collaboration (UIC) in Brazil through the lens of co-authorship of publications compound with other data sources that bring information about companies' characterization. When assessing UIC with a co-authorship output, a great number of investigations concentrated solely on the academic side of U-I cooperation providing shallow qualitative information about the particularities of companies participating in UIC. This study is based on a listing of all co-authored publications jointly realized by Brazilian universities and researchers affiliated in domestic companies from 1972 to 2021. The preliminary results provided information about the evolution of UIC in Brazil by considering sectors, size and geographical location of companies. These findings are original and contribute to enrich the set of evidence over the evolution of UIC in the national context and to advancing on methodological approaches to assess characteristics of companies that participate in UIC.

Introduction

University-industry collaboration (UIC) has been considered an important driver for competitiveness in the businesses sectors. The UIC types of relationship have grown in importance as a central strategy for science, technology and innovation policies worldwide (Brito Cruz, 2021; Garcia and Suzigan, 2021, Garcia et al., 2019, Gielfi et al., 2017; Poyago-Theotoky, Beath, and Siegel, 2002; Tijssen, 2012). The literature highlights relevant outputs and outcomes promoted by UIC such as: promoting processes of technological catching-up (Mazzoleni and Nelson, 2007; Albuquerque 2001); promoting knowledge and technology transfer (Garcia et al., 2020), and its positive effects on academic productivity (D'Este and Perkmann, 2011 ; Garcia and Suzigan, 2021).

To generate evidence about UICs in their different arrangements, and in different geographical contexts, is a methodological challenge. Although recent advancements in using co-authorship in publications, patent registration and other secondary data sources, there are several bottlenecks that need to be resolved.

One of the main difficulties is assessing, from secondary data sources, the sectoral, geographical, and size particularities of companies participating in UIC. This is mainly due to the absence of secondary data sources that inform beyond the identification of co-authorship in scientific and technological publications and in patents. Furthermore, even disambiguating company IDs is a recurring burden to describe the UIC.

We still have huge problems in disambiguating companies' names, and creating reliable company IDs to link them to other databases that may inform basic elements that characterize companies, such as size (both in local and in global levels); geographical location (headquarters and local branches that are not standardized), composition and qualification of human resources dedicated to R&D and innovation (in local and global levels). Likewise, linking companies

appearing in co-authorship with data of R&D and innovation efforts is also a valuable information that depends on the standardization of company IDs.

Having these data linkages reasonably structured it would be possible to understand in greater detail the intensity, drivers, and relevance that UIC present in a country or in a particular context of interest. To date, this sort of analyses has been based on simple co-authorship information from publications' data sources, without normalization of company IDs and with shallow – if any – qualitative information about companies' activities in the place authors have developed research in cooperation with universities (Abramo et al., 2009, 2020; Lundberg et al., 2006; Krieger et al., 2021; Pechter and Kakinuma's, 1999; Wang et al., 2005; Tijssen, Wilk, and Leeuwe; 2009).

In this research, we seek to contribute to solve some of those bottlenecks, through the study of co-authorship between Brazilian universities and companies in publications extracted from a large source of bibliometric data. For this aim, we are carrying out two sequential steps.

The first one is the standardization of company IDs in a sample of publications featuring co-authorship between Brazilian universities and national and multinational companies from 1972 to 2021. A process of disambiguation of primary information on the affiliation of companies is proposed and applied, allowing to link companies appearing in publications, with other data sources. The second one is to cross that information with one of the main relevant companies' data source in Brazil, the Annual Report of Social Information (RAIS, in the original acronym) which contains basic characterization of all companies operating in the national territory.

We correlate a sample of disambiguated companies with the RAIS data source, obtaining information such as the industrial classification of the companies (compatible with the International Industrial Classification Standard - ISIC), and the size and location of companies that appear in the affiliations of publications.

For the time being, we could create information about the evolution of UIC in terms of sectors, size and geographical location of companies. These findings are original and contribute to enrich the set of evidence over the evolution of UIC in the national context.

The aim of the present “research in progress” is to contribute to the analysis of university-enterprise collaborations, departing from co-authorship and crossing different data sources in order to overcome some of the above-mentioned bottlenecks, particularly the normalization of companies' IDs and the connections with other secondary data sources that may add important qualitative information about the evolution of UIC in Brazil.

The next step in this research is to cross-reference the companies' data with the information that is now being extracted from the set of publications on areas of knowledge, venues of publication and universities involved.

Theoretical background

The awareness of the potential economic benefits from the UIC has prompted many countries to develop and promote policies to support this relationship which was accompanied by an increasing number of scholars that focused on analyzing trends in the industry-university relationship (Pechter and Kakinuma, 1999; Tijssen, 2005; Wang et al., 2005; Krieger et al., 2021, Cruz, 2021; Sun et al., 2021; Abramo et al, 2021).

There are several ways for universities and firms to form partnerships, which may differ across countries (Albuquerque et al., 2015) and are usually sector and technology-specific (Bodas Freitas, 2008; Gielfi et al., 2017). Due to the heterogeneity of relationships, there are many methodological challenges in measuring and assessing the diversity of university-industry collaborations (Pechter and Kakinuma, 1999; Gielfi et al., 2017). The research literature has focused on an output indicator of co-authorship which became a standard way of measuring research collaborations since the mid and late 1990s (Tijssen, 2005; Lundberg et al., 2006; Tijssen, 2012).

Although co-authorship is not a perfect indicator and may not capture all industrial collaborations, it can be used as a proxy measure for university-industry research cooperation, which indicates a high level of involvement between both academic and industrial researchers (Pechter and Kakinuma, 1999; Tijssen, 2005; Lundberg et al., 2006; Tijssen, Leeuwen and Wijk, 2009; Tijssen, 2012; Gielfi et al., 2017).

Co-authored publications can indicate the access to an often informal network and can suggest diffusion of knowledge and skills, and access to key research staff and complementary research activity (Bozeman and Corley, 2004). Analyzing collaboration through the lens of co-authorship can comprehend the magnitude and intensity of collaboration (Melin and Person, 1996; Tijssen, Wilk and Leeuwen, 2009).

In an attempt to validate the use of university-industry co-authorship as a performance indicator, Tijssen, Wilk, and Leeuwe's (2009) assessment aimed at understanding which universities were major suppliers of research services to the industry by using co-authored research published during 2002–2006 between university researchers and private researchers. The authors concluded that university-industry co-authorship offers an interesting source of empirical data for domestic and international comparisons of research universities.

Firms and publication characteristics were addressed on Pechter and Kakinuma's (1999) analysis of co-authorship as a measure of university-industry research interaction in Japan and by Wang et al. (2005) in China. The findings of both studies indicated that co-authorship between industry and universities rose during the analyzed period. Wang et al (2005) however, emphasized that different regions have different collaborative patterns corresponding to economic, technological, and scientific development levels.

Lundberg et al. (2006) investigated how well university-industry collaborations could be identified and described using co-authorship data. By comparing co-authorship data with industrial funding to a medical university in Sweden from 1993 to 2003, authors concluded that both metrics (co-authorship and funding indicators) when used alone provide incomplete results and these metrics should be used together to understand university-industry performance better. Abramo et al. (2009) investigated public–private research collaboration between Italian universities and domestic industry. Authors applied a bibliometric type of approach based on a listing of all co-authored publications in international journals that are jointly realized by Italian university scientists and researchers in the private sector in the 2001–2003 triennium. Results indicate that most collaborations occur in medicine and chemistry. A complementary study developed by Abramo, D'Angelo and Di Costa (2020) however have found that on average public-private co-authored publications in Italy have lower impact than intra-university co-authored publications, and represent a lower share of highly-cited publications.

According to Garcia et al. (2015), university-industry collaboration in Brazil is characterized by a markedly uneven geographical distribution and concentration in specific sectors like mining, oil and petrochemicals, agribusiness, and aerospace industries (Bodas-Freitas et al., 2013). The literature commonly addresses the relationship between university and industry in Brazil based on its impact on academic productivity. Some studies emphasize the benefits of this collaboration by stressing that engagement with industry through long-term projects enables knowledge transfer, accelerates the exploitation of new inventions, and increases academic productivity (Garcia et al., 2017; Garcia et al., 2019a, Garcia et al., 2019b).

Gielfi et al. (2017) develop a relevant study of university-industry research collaboration in the Brazilian oil industry by investigating collaboration between the Brazilian state-controlled oil company Petrobras and universities from 1980 to 2014. Findings show an increasing collaboration between Petrobras and Brazilian universities, resulting in an enlargement of its network collaboration and reinforcing its knowledge base.

Finally, the efforts made by Brito Cruz (2021) present the evolution of UIC in Brazil. By analyzing the quantity and intensity of university/business co-authorship in scientific articles (among other indicators), the study highlights that the volume of articles with business co-authors has been increasing as a percentage of the total scientific output of universities in Brazil but there is still potential for fruitful university-business interactions when comparing the Brazilian share of co-authored with business at 2.4% with other countries, such as South Korea, Germany, and France, which range from 3.8% to 4.4%.

The analysis of UIC in Brazil follows the global trend, with few case studies covering only some dimensions of the university-industry relationship. Potential results from such approach are relevant by allowing us to identify technical-scientific fields that are aligned with private demand and public offer of knowledge, and also highlights the sectors and fields of knowledge in which the university- corporate collaboration is weak or absent (Abramo et al., 2009).

Methodology

Initially, a list of publications from the Scopus database with articles co-authored by companies and Brazilian universities was obtained. This list brought companies by the name that appeared in the author's affiliation. The search in SCOPUS was done using the IDs for all universities in Brazil and IDs for all entities categorized in SCOPUS as companies plus entities identified among the list of non-categorized entities that had suffixes denoting a corporate entity in Brazil, such as LTDA, SA, S.A., Companhia and EIRELI.

This list had about 5,000 observations in the period covering 1972 to 2021. Companies' names appeared without any standardization. Among the most common problems were name abbreviations and variations of the most different forms for the same company; companies that in fact were not companies but non-profit research organizations, names in Portuguese and English. The same type of incorrect information was observed in the addresses of the companies: some with complete addresses, others with abbreviations, personal addresses and even locations not found in any available directories. A huge task to organize and sort out. A first automatic analysis was performed to group companies with similar names (above 85% similarity using Levenshtein distance (Rani and Singh, 2018)). This matching process of the list against the RAIS list is computationally intensive given the size of the later, so both lists were placed in a dataset set inside Google BigQuery (Fernandes and Bernardino, 2015). After the matching, a manual analysis was performed to verify the correctness of the grouping. This

process was repeated until no more ambiguities could be verified. In order to have information on the companies, it was needed to identify the ID number (the CNPJ, in the national acronym) of all the companies on the list. This allowed us to go a little further in the disambiguation process. A company may have one or more CNPJs, depending on its activities and the number of branches it has.

The following step was to find information about companies' sectoral classification and size (measured by the number of employees). For this end, we match our list with the RAIS database. RAIS is updated every year along with the information of new and closed companies as well as their changes in details such as employees, addresses and other characteristics.

The match was conducted by comparing the names of the disambiguated list to the names registered in the RAIS data source by a Levenshtein algorithm in the Python programming language with a machine with enough memory built on the Google Cloud Platform directly reading the BigQuery tables.

Several more companies appeared as possible matches to the then disambiguated list. The match with RAIS generated a new necessity of disambiguation. The remaining list was manually filtered.

Finally, we obtained a list of 1972 unique companies, along with the information of their names, registration of identity, economic sector, number of employees, employees in R&D and main geographic location. Also, the relative participation of some prominent companies over the evolution of co-authorship will be analysed.

Statistical analyses, both descriptive and multivariate, are now being employed in an attempt to find out patterns of cooperation and reveal how cooperation has evolved among companies and universities, in which sectors, areas of knowledge and geographic regions.

Preliminary results

Although in its initial phase, our research has shown interesting preliminary results.

- Our methodology for searching for co-authorships between Brazilian universities and companies obtained a set of publications superior to that automatically generated by the Scival platform. This is due to the use of a broader range of search terms that identify business sectors. The percentage of the highest number of publications with co-authorship obtained by our methodology varies according to the time-period. In recent years (2019-2021) we managed to retrieve 50% more co-authored articles than Scival.
- There is an impressive growth rate of co-authored papers in the past 30 years. The overall growth rate was around 17% per year between 1991 and 2008 and 6% per year between 2010 and 2021.
- Co-authorship involving companies not established in Brazil has grown at a faster pace than companies established in the national territory in the last ten years.
- Publications co-authored with companies have evolved from a strong concentration in exact and earth sciences in the 1980s to a more balanced distribution among areas such as agriculture, health, biological, engineering and exact sciences.

Next steps

A descriptive and a multivariate analysis trying to characterize companies are now being performed. Results will be available at the time of the ISSI conference. A discussion with the literature and the advancements on the methodological approaches will be made available.

We will also address analyses crossing data from companies with data that will be extracted from publications (fields of knowledge, venues of publications, types – public, private, federal state level - and geographical locations of universities).

We hope to answer research questions about what sectors, company sizes, areas of expertise and geographic contexts are being developed within UICs in Brazil; what are the contributions that the methodology adds to the current state of the art; to what extent the methodological approach can be adopted by other countries and contexts; among other related issues.

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